

HESANDA – MONASH NODE

Master guidelines. November 2023

Abstract

Health Data Australia (HDA) contains descriptions of health datasets, provided by the data owners and stored elsewhere. To get access to the data, researchers submit a request to the owner, who will review and determine whether access can be granted.

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Health Data Australia

Overview of Health Data Australia

Health Data Australia (HDA) helps researchers discover and access health data. They do not store the data itself but provide descriptions of the data from their data publishing partners. Using HDA, researchers can search these descriptions, find data of use to do their research, then request access to it. The request will be sent to the owner of the data to review. Data owners receive email notifications about new data requests and can then log into the HDA Data Request platform to review the request and determine whether access can be granted and then respond to the researcher requesting access. If the request is approved, the owner arranges for the researcher to be given access to the data.

The dataset descriptions ('metadata') contained on HDA help researchers understand the kinds of data that exist and assess whether a dataset may be of value to their research, without the need to actually access the data. In addition to metadata, data owners provide other documentation describing the data they hold, such as study protocols and data dictionaries.

Using HDA, researchers can search for data, save their searches, submit and manage data requests.

HeSANDAs

The information on Health Data Australia was provided by the HeSANDAs network. HeSANDAs is a network of 72 health research organisations working collaboratively as nine 'nodes' to give researchers better access to health data. For more information about HeSANDAs, see [here](#). Health Data Australia launched in July 2023. Over the next five years, it will be expanded to incorporate a wider array of data collections from different health research studies, as well as government and health service data. [Here](#) is the link to the Platform.

The HeSANDAs Network

There are 9 HeSANDAs nodes that represent 72 health research organisations across Australia

Melbourne Academic Centre for Health (MACH) Clinical Trials Consortium Node <i>Administered by:</i> The University of Melbourne	Queensland Node <i>Administered by:</i> Health Translation Queensland
Mental Health Node <i>Administered by:</i> Deakin University	South Australia Node <i>Administered by:</i> South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute (SAHMRI)
Monash and Partners Node <i>Administered by:</i> Monash University	Sydney Health Partners Node <i>Administered by:</i> NHMRC Clinical Trials Centre at The University of Sydney
National Cancer Cooperative Trials Groups Node <i>Administered by:</i> Australasian Leukaemia and Lymphoma Group (ALLG)	West Australian Node <i>Administered by:</i> Curtin University
Northern Australia Node <i>Administered by:</i> Menzies School of Health Research	

Logos at the bottom: Monash Partners Academic Health Science Centre, MONASH University, Australian Research Data Commons.

Figure 1. The HeSANDAs network

How to Login Using Australian Access Federation (AAF)

This section provides a step-by-step guide on accessing the Health Data Australia portal by logging in with valid AAF credentials.

What is AAF?

The Australian Access Federation (AAF) is an authentication and authorisation service that allows individuals to securely access online resources and services provided by participating organisations in Australia. It streamlines the access process by providing a unified set of login credentials. By using AAF, you can log in to the Health Data Australia portal without the need for creating separate credentials.

For more information about AAF, see: <https://aaf.edu/au>

About obtaining an AAF account, please refer to: [How to obtain an AAF account](#), or see the next section.

Why log in to HDA?

While you can browse metadata and conduct searches in the Health Data Australia (HDA) portal without logging in, there are several key functionalities that are only available to users with an account. By logging in to HDA, you will obtain a MyHDA user profile page and gain access to the following functionalities:

- Save a search query.
- Save a health dataset.
- Request access to a health dataset and track the process.

For more information, see: [MyHDA](#), or the following section

Steps to log in using AAF

Step 1: Navigate to the portal and locate the Login button

On every page in the HDA portal, the "LOG IN" button is located at the top-right corner of the header. Click on it to proceed to the Keycloak authentication page.

Welcome to Health Data Australia

Fig 1.1 The home page with the LOG IN button on the top

After being navigated to the Keycloak authentication page, click the button "AAF Login". You will be redirected to the AAF Central login page with a list of organisations.

Step 2: Select your organisation

On the AAF Central login page, you will see a list of organisations that are part of the AAF network. Find and select the organisation that you're affiliated with from the list.

This could be your university, research institution, or any other participating organisation. You can also search for your organisation using the provided search bar.

Login to AAF Central

AAF central provides authentication and identity bridging between disparate authentication protocols such as SAML IdP to OpenID Connect RP.

Please select your organisation below, you will be redirected to complete the login process.

Search for your organisation

AAF Virtual Home

Actors Centre Australia

AIMS

Continue to your organisation

Remember my organisation

Australian Access Federation
Test Federation

[Current AAF status](#)
[Contact AAF support](#)

Fig 1.2 The AAF Central Login page

Step 3: Enter your credentials and authenticate with your organisation

After selecting your organisation, you will be redirected to your organisation's login page.

On the login page, you can enter your AAF login credentials, which usually consist of your organisational username and password. If you are unsure about your login credentials, contact your organisation's IT support or helpdesk for assistance.

Once you have entered your login credentials, click on the "Login" or "Authenticate" button to proceed. AAF will communicate with your organization's identity provider to verify your credentials and authenticate your access.

Step 4: Access the HDA portal

After successfully logging in and granting any necessary permissions, you will be redirected back to the HDA portal. You will notice that the items on the top-right menu has been updated to the one below:

Welcome to Health Data Australia

Fig 1.3 The home page after you successfully logged in

Now you should have full access to MyHDA and the full list of functionalities provided by HDA.

MyHDA – HeSANDA

About MyHDA

After [logging in to Health Data Australia \(HDA\) using your AAF credentials](#), you'll gain access to your MyHDA user profile page and unlock the full functionalities of HDA. MyHDA comprises four sections:

- My saved searches
 - Allows you to organise, review and refresh your saved search queries.
- My saved records
 - A centralised section to view the datasets that you bookmarked before.
- My saved requests
 - Allows you to resume editing your unfinished and unsubmitted data requests. Once you started filling in an Express of Interest (EOI) form, you can save it at anytime and come back to resume editing it in the "My saved requests" table.
- My submitted requests
 - Allows you to check the status of the submitted data requests, and take actions accordingly.

Each is designed to provide convenient access and simple management of your saved datasets, searches, and data access requests.

The detailed features and available functionalities will be introduced in each tab accordingly.

The example below shows a sample MyHDA page for a user:

My HDA

1 User Profile & Logout

2 My Saved Searches

3 My Saved Records

4 My Saved Data Requests

5 My Submitted Data Requests

Fig 1.1 A sample MyHDA page

How to view a Health Dataset in HeSANDA (all)

Record view page overview

Once you have discovered health datasets of interest, the Health Data Australia (HDA) portal provides a comprehensive overview of each dataset's metadata, providing essential information about the dataset and the access option. You can also save the health dataset to your MyHDA profile page, which gives you quick access to this dataset in the future.

One of the prominent features of the record view page is the ability to examine the dataset's connections to other entities. By navigating through the graph visualisation and the listed related parties, you can get a clear understanding about the origin and sourcing of the health dataset, i.e. the funder and the collector. The related study section provided additional details about the study to which the dataset is related. This information expands the scope of understanding by providing valuable context and background information about the dataset.

The figure below shows an example of a record view page in HDA and the name of different sections on the page

Fig 1.1 Record View Page in HDA

Title Bar

The title bar on the record view page presents the most essential information about the health dataset. It includes the dataset's title and the name of its publisher, allowing users to quickly identify and understand the dataset they are reviewing. An icon in the top-right corner specifically indicates the record type.

Data Access and Saving Options

This section provides you with intuitive functionality to interact with your desired datasets. Clicking the button "Access the data" will redirect you to an Express of Interest (EOI) form, in which you can fill in detailed information about yourself and the project you're working on, in order to be granted approval to access the health dataset.

Clicking the button "Save to MyHDA" allows you to save the dataset to MyHDA profile page, so that you can quickly retrieve the dataset for future reference and analysis.

For a more detailed instruction about how to request access to a health dataset, see: [How to Request Access to a Health Dataset](#)

For more information about the saved datasets, see: [MyHDA > My Saved Data Requests](#)

Dataset Description

The Dataset Description section serves as a reference point that provides an overview of the health dataset.

Graph Visualisation

The interactive Graph Visualisation section offers intuitive functionalities for you to explore different connections associated to the health dataset. This powerful feature allows you to uncover relationships with various individuals, organisations, and other health datasets on multiple levels. Different vertices represent different type of entities. The arrows between these vertices indicates the way they are related. You can also double-click any vertex on the graph to see if it's connected with other vertices, so that you can have a more comprehensive view about how data and people/organisations are connected.

For a more detailed instruction about how to use the graph visualisation, see: [Graph Visualisation](#)

Related Parties

This section introduces the individuals and organisations that are related to the current health dataset in text format. For more information about the related parties, see: [Related Parties](#)

Subjects

Each subject in the dataset represents a descriptive element that highlights the primary focus of the health dataset. It aids in the discoverability of datasets and facilitates searching, filtering, and categorisation of datasets that align with your research interests or information requirements. Clicking a subject will redirect you to a search result page displaying all the datasets associated with that subject in their metadata. This allows for convenient exploration and enhances your ability to find relevant and valuable information for your own research needs.

Identifiers

The Identifiers section lists all the available identifiers of the current health dataset and will provide redirection to the identifier if the identifier is resolvable.

Related Study

In HDA, every health dataset is related to a study. This section serves as a valuable resource for understanding the context, background, and additional information related to the dataset's associated study. For more information about the related study, see: [Related Study](#)

How do I get set up to use HDA Data Request

What is a Point Of Contact (POC)?

On the HDA Data Request platform, a 'POC' is the person that has been designated by the data owner to receive and respond to data requests submitted to the platform. The POC may be the data owner, the data custodian, or someone they nominate. For the Monash Node – this is Helix, at Monash University. All HDA requests will go to the helix support email which is monitored by several Helix staff (helix@monash.edu).

A POC is responsible for:

- Receiving data requests from the HDA Data Request ARDC Data Request platform
- Actioning the data request in accordance with the governance arrangements determined by the data owner
- Actively reviewing and tracking the progress of data requests within the HDA Data Request ARDC Data Request platform
- Responding to data requests in a timely manner.
- Liaising with the data about the progress of their request

(Please note: The POC is an administrative role within the platform and is not intended or designed to replace the governance arrangements or roles determined by the data owner. A data owner may choose to act as a POC, or they may delegate someone to act on their behalf. The details of these arrangements are at the discretion of the data owner. The Monash node has designated Helix as the contact for data requests through HDA)

(Important note for existing users: If you are an existing user and would like to add or change the details of a POC, please contact: hesanda@ardc.edu.au)

How to login to your HDA Data Request account

Once an HDA Data Request account has been created for you, you should receive an email notification from one of the NII Services administrators inviting you to join the team.

By default, you will be given access to Jira Service Management. Verify that you have received the email then click 'Join the team.'

Your team is waiting for you to join them

 HeSANDA has invited you to collaborate on ARDC Data Request

[Join the team](#)

Here's what **HeSANDA** and your team are using to work seamlessly and accomplish more, together:

Cheers,
The Atlassians

The next screen will ask you to complete your login registration for the POC email address specified in the HDA Data Request account creation request (see 'your HDA Data Request account'). Enter your Full Name and password then click ' Sign up

ATLASSIAN

Sign up to join your team

We need a few details, to create an account for **hda.test@ardc.edu.au**

Enter full name

Create password

By signing up, I accept the Atlassian [Cloud Terms of Service](#) and acknowledge the [Privacy Policy](#).

Sign up

ATLASSIAN

One account for Jira, Confluence, Trello and [more](#).

This page is protected by reCAPTCHA and the Google [Privacy Policy](#) and [Terms of Service](#) apply.

If you belong to an organisation that enforces the organisation's Identity Provider (IdP) for authentication, login to HDA Data Request as you would normally do in your local systems using the enrolled email address.

When sign up is completed, you will be redirected to the HDA DARMS login page.

In the future, you can login to HDA Data Request by navigating to <https://ardc-datarequest.atlassian.net>

Click ' Login ' and then enter your email and the password you just created. You should then see a screen such as the following when logged in.:

Notes:

'Your work' (figure above) is the default screen/homepage when you log in to the HDA Data Request platform.

To change your default homepage to the HDA POC Dashboard, follow the instructions on 'How to change your data request homepage' below.

How to change your default data request homepage

1. Navigate to your user account profile icon on the top right corner of the screen.
2. Select 'Personal Settings' as per screenshot below.

1. On 'Your Jira homepage section, select 'Dashboards' from the drop-down list
2. Navigate to the end of the screen and click 'Save changes' to save your settings

Personal settings

Setting your dashboard as the homepage also sets it as the default page when you click the ARDC logo on the upper left-hand corner of the screen.

How to view all of data requests

Go to <https://ardc-datarequest.atlassian.net>

1. Enter your login credentials.
2. Click login.
 - a. Click 'Dashboards' on the top left-hand side of the screen, then click 'Health Data Australia POC Dashboard'.

You can change your default homepage to the POC Dashboard and skip this step by following the instructions on "How to change your default data request homepage'.

You should see a screen similar to the image below. If there is no pie chart or items listed in any of the sections, then no data requests have been received.

How to view a new data request

POCs have two options to view a newly created data request:

- Directly access the data request from the data request email notification; or
- Login to HDA Data Request and access the request via the HDA POC Dashboard

From the email notification:

The POC will receive an email from Health Data Australia each time a new data request is received. The email contains valuable information about the request:

- Request ID - which has the ID number that links directly to the data request in HDA Data Request

- Status - normally 'Submitted' if it is a new request
- Dataset Name - the full name of the dataset
- DOI - a resolvable DOI link, if available
- Attachment(s) - the EOI form and any other files attached to the request such as the Ethics Approval document

Via the HDA POC dashboard:

In the HDA POC Dashboard, locate the panel which is titled 'HDA: All NEW Requests (SUBMITTED Status)'. These are all new requests which have not been actioned yet.

Health Data Australia POC Dashboard

HDA: All NEW Requests (SUBMITTED status)		
Key	Summary	Created
HDA-335	THE TULIP STUDY: Telehealth Use In Pregnancy - Prior-to-release Test health dataset 29	27/Jun/23
HDA-331	ALLG NHL26 A Phase 2 Study of patients treated for relapsed Follicular Lymphoma: with Revlimid (Registered Trademark) consolidation added to Rituximab maintenance therapy in those remaining Positron Emission Tomography (PET) positive	22/Jun/23
HDA-329	A Strategy of High-Dose Lenalidomide in Combination with Epigenetic Therapies for Relapsed or Refractory Acute Myeloid Leukaemia (AML)- Phase II (AMLM17)	22/Jun/23
HDA-325	DAB Trial Dataset	22/Jun/23
HDA-324	A feasibility study of lorazepam for anxiety in palliative care (LORAZEPAM Study)	22/Jun/23

1-5 of 96 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 >

🔄 2 minutes ago

The first 5 new requests will be displayed by default. You can click 'Created' to toggle the display from descending to ascending or vice versa.

Click the blue number at the bottom to display the whole list or click the page number on the lower right to navigate to the other data requests.

1. Identify the data request of interest and click its hyperlink, either by clicking the Summary or the key.
2. You will be taken to a page containing information about the data request, including:
 - The person making the request (listed as the 'Reporter')
 - The dataset being requested
 - The DOI for the dataset
 - A PDF containing the full details of the request (the 'Expression of Interest or 'EOI' form)
 - Any additional documents provided by the Requestor (e.g. copies of ethics approval)

To view and/or download the EOI and other documents, click on the links in the Attachments section

How to view the Requestor's ethics approval

In the EOI form, Requestors are asked to provide information regarding their ethics approval. They can also upload any relevant documentation. Both the EOI form and additional documentation will be listed in the Attachments section.

Please note: The Requestor may be seeking your in-principle support to share data (e.g. as part of a funding or ethics application), and may not currently have ethics approval. They should clearly indicate this in their data request.

To view information about the Requestor's ethics approval:

1. After opening the new data request, click on the attachment to access the EOI form.
2. Details of their ethics approval will be in the section titled 'Ethics Information' at the end of the PDF.
3. If the Requestor has provided additional documentation (e.g. a copy of their ethics approval) this will be included as a separate file in the Attachments section. Click on that attachment to view its contents or any information regarding their ethics approval.
4. Navigate back to the data request by either closing the 'View attachment' window or going back to your browser if you downloaded the attachment to your computer.

How to contact the Requestor about the data request

If you would like additional information or clarification about the data request, you can contact the Requestor by adding a comment to the data request. At the bottom of the data request page, click the 'Reply to customer' hyperlink.

Make sure that you are in the 'Reply to Customer' tab when you save your attachment. Any comments added under 'Add internal note' will only be visible to watchers and POCs and no notification will be sent the requestor.

Activity

Show: [All](#) [Comments](#) [History](#) [Work log](#) [Approvals](#) Newest first ↕

AR Add internal note [Reply to customer](#)

Aa ▾ B I ... A ▾ ☰ ▾ + ▾ ↻ Canned responses

Type @ to mention and notify someone.

Save Cancel

Type in a comment, and click 'Save'.

The Requestor and the watchers will receive a notification email with the details of your comment.

Please bear in mind that requestors cannot reply to emails sent to them via HDA Data Request. You would need to indicate in your comment how they should get in touch with you.

You may add any relevant communications between you and the requestor by adding a comment under 'Add Internal Note' (Remember that adding them under 'Reply to customer' will send them notifications).

How to update the status of a data request:

In the data request summary page, navigate to the status on the right-hand panel.

Click the dropdown button, and select the new action or status.

You will only see the actions or statuses that you can perform or you have permission to at a particular stage in the process. As per sample screenshot above, all new requests can only be withdrawn or reviewed.

Left hand texts indicate the actions (i.e. Start Review) while the right-hand texts (i.e. Review in Progress) indicate the new status once an action is performed.

The status of the data request will now be updated and reflected on the summary page dashboard.

Refer to Workflows and Statuses above for information on the different actions and statuses available.

The Requestor (and watchers) will receive an email notifying them that the status of their data request has changed.

How to view dataset request metrics

The HDA POC Dashboard not only allows you to view the list of data requests in different statuses but it also gives an overall picture of all the requests received represented in a pie chart displayed on the right-hand panel of the dashboard.

Depending on the number of data requests in different statuses, the pie chart should display:

- The number of new data requests you have received (Submitted)
- The number of data requests currently being reviewed by you (Review in Progress)
- The number of data requests for which In-Principle Approval was granted and pending release of the dataset(s) (In-Principle Approval)
- The number of datasets requests that are awaiting additional information from the data requestor (Modifications Requested)
- The number of data requests that have been approved and distributed by you (Data Released)
- The number of data requests you denied (Denied)
- The number of data requests that have been withdrawn by the data requestor (Withdrawn)
- The number of data requests that have been discontinued as agreed between you and the data requestor (Discontinued)

Figure 1. HDA Data Request metrics

If a Status is not displayed on the chart, this means you don't have issues in that status.

How to manage the Dashboards

Health Data Australia Dashboard is managed by the HDA project administrators. Please [contact](#) them if you have suggestions or questions.

How to add an existing dashboard to your "Favourite Dashboards" list

Login to Jira at <https://ardc-datarequest.atlassian.net/>

At the top menu click on Dashboards then select View all dashboards.

1. In the Search box, enter the name (or search term) of the dashboard you are after (i.e. POC). Hit enter to start searching.
2. All the dashboards matching your search criteria will be displayed for all projects you have access to will be displayed.
3. Click on the "star" beside Health Data Australia POC Dashboard title.

Once selected, the star shape should change its colour to yellow which indicates that the dashboard is already in your favourites list and should always be one of the selections in your dashboard list when you log in to Jira.

You can use the different filters available (Owner, Project, Group) to narrow down your search results when searching for a dashboard.

How to add your own personal or private filter

A lot of dashboard widgets are based on saved filters therefore it is important to understand how to create a filter. Filters can be private or personal or shared with certain people or role or groups.

1. Once logged in to Jira, go to the Filters > Advanced issue search or Search > Advanced issue search

- The Search window be displayed. By default, the basic search will be displayed. Filter your search results according to your requirements. Choose the project, issue type, status, or any specific search term, as necessary. You may add more fields to include in your search criteria by clicking + More.

You can do JQL search if you have a more complicated search. Click on Switch to JCL to do this as per screenshot below.

- Once you have selected your own filters, click on the Search button to display the search result.
- If you are happy with the search result, go to the upper left-hand corner of the screen and then save your filter by clicking on the Save as button just beside Search

Add your filter name (choose the name that best describes it especially if you are going to share it with other users) and then click on the 'Submit' button to save.

1. You can share it with others by clicking the Share button on the upper right hand corner of the screen and then add the username or email address of the person you wish to share your filter with (Note: Users you share your filter with will only view the issues they have access to depending on their roles in Jira. If you think this filter should be shared with everyone, please send an email to [ARDC NII Services](mailto:ARDC.NII.Services) so that the same filter can be created using a functional account for future maintenance).
2. Your filter is now ready to be used.

How to create a dashboard

Now that you know how to create different filters, you are now ready to create a dashboard.

Login to Jira at <https://ardc.atlassian.net/>

1. At the top menu click on Dashboards then select View all dashboards.
2. Click the 'Create dashboard' button on the upper right-hand corner of the screen.

Type in the name of the dashboard, the description. Select the appropriate user, group or project (and role) you wish to give 'Viewer' or 'Editor' access. Click Add.

Create dashboard

Name *

Description

Viewers

Project Add

Private

Editors

Private Only you Add

Private

Save Cancel

AT this stage, you are only allowed to share your dashboard to either

- Project: The whole HDA project members (from all organisations)
- Group: the groups you belong to (hda-pocs is your default group if you are a POC or had-watchers is your default group if you are a watcher)
- My organisation: Any logged in user in HDA Data Request (this option only becomes different from the HDA Project if there are other projects you have access to other than HDA available. At this stage, there is only 1 project).

Click Save when you are done.

Now you are ready to add gadgets to the dashboard.

Click on Add Gadget button then select the gadget you would like to be displayed in the dashboard.

Click on the Add button to add your selected gadget it to the dashboard.

Follow the sample instructions below to add a gadget to your dashboard.

Example: How to add a 'Filter Results' gadget:

Search for 'Filter Results' and click 'Add'.

The gadget configuration window will be displayed

1. Saved filter - Search for the filter you just created or any existing filter.
2. Number of results - this defines the number of rows/entries that will be displayed in the gadget
3. Columns to display - you have the flexibility to customise which fields you wish to display in columns by adding them using the drop-down list provided. You can also re-order the columns as you wish.
4. There is an option to do auto-refresh but this is not necessary.
5. click Save when done.

How to update or edit a dashboard

Please take note that you are only able to update or edit dashboards that you created or you own. If you wish to suggest edits to the global HDA POC Dashboard, please send an email to [ARDC NII Services](#) team.

1. Login to Jira at <https://ardc-datarequest.atlassian.net/> if you are not already logged in
2. At the top menu click on Dashboards then select View all dashboards (see Fig 1.1) if the dashboard you wish to edit is not in your favourites list else, directly go to the dashboard you wish to edit by clicking on its name.
3. On the upper right-hand corner of the screen, click the Edit button.

Editing a gadget

Go to the gadget that you wish to edit. Click on the ellipsis icon on the upper right and select Configure as per below.

1. Edit/change the settings and Save it when done (refer to an example above).
2. If you are done with all the edits you wanted to do in the dashboard, click Done to exit edit mode.

Editing or changing the dashboard layout

Click on Change layout button on the top right corner of the screen. The layout options will be displayed as below. Select the layout you prefer.

You can change the layout of the dashboard and all existing gadgets will not be impacted expect how they are displayed on the screen so feel free to change the layout as you please.

You can drag and drop the gadget to an area on the dashboard that you want them displayed.

When you are happy with the display, click Done to exit edit mode.